

Influence of Project Resource Planning on Performance of Elephant Conservation at TSAVO National Park, Kenya

Akuno Eileen Awuor¹, Wanyoike Daniel²

1. *Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology*

2. *Senior Lecturer, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology*

Abstract: The aim of the study is to determine the influence of project resource planning on performance of elephant conservation at Tsavo National Park. The specific objectives of the study were to determine the influence of project resource planning on performance of elephant conservation at Tsavo National Park. Two theories of resource-based theory and planning theory were used. From the study, it was revealed that resource planning affected performance of elephant conservation projects to a large extent. The relationship between resource planning and conservation project performance was established to be statistically significant (value $(p= 0.000)$). From the finding, the study recommends that project managers should develop a resource plan that should contain every aspect that pertains to every resource necessary for project from beginning to end. One that should be monitored regularly.

Keywords: resource planning, project success, project planning, performance

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Planning is a very important part of a project regarding project performance and project success. It is a continuous process throughout the delivery of a project. (Idoro, 2012). Project Planning involves an arrangement of stages, duties, and tasks hierarchically arranged to be executed in projects as explained by (Kerzner, 2013) on project planning techniques and systematic approach on projects planning. Thus, Project planning involves the implementation of skills, practices, and comprehension of tools to the activities of a project to outlive the expectations and needs of the stakeholders in a project and ensure sustainability. Project planning involves setting goals, deciding what the project entails (Müller & Jugdev, 2012). According to Chinyio & Olomolaiye (2010) people who get what they want do so because they have clear goals and develop plans and schedules to achieve the goals. They assume personal responsibility for implementing these plans. Goals give directions to what one is involved in goals promote enthusiasm. Inherent in any goal setting is some level of effort required to achieve it.

Globally project planning is widely thought to be an important contributor to project success. Project planning entails scheduling of the various activities comprising the project activities and how they interrelate (Murphy & Ledwith, 2016). The activities comprise the legal or regulatory requirements, procurement processes that include seeking for development projects and funding institution approvals, activities of the funding institutions leading to credit award and the actual site works. The planning aims at optimizing time, cost and procurement of human capacity for development projects within the legal, regulatory and policy framework existing for each specific project (Jabareen, 2016). The project environment of developing countries on the African continent is fraught with many difficulties; these difficulties impair several of their success (Du Plessis, 2015).

Project Planning is a crucial aspect for sustainably and responsibly growth conservation of projects in Kenya. A sequence of processes including several techniques and methods of project planning management are essential in project management. Kenya has allowed private individuals to run conservancies 75% of Kenya's spectacular wildlife is outside National Parks on private and community land. This is so because conservancies involve entire communities in preserving wildlife and thus the community's benefit from revenue sharing (KWS, 2013)

Project performance is the most important confirmation that project funds have been utilized appropriately to deliver the project goals and targets. Nevertheless, many projects still fail to achieve and realize expected benefits

(Bailey, Farmer, Crocker, Jessop and Jones 2012). Hence, this has led to project delays and cost overrun in some projects. Globally, project failures have often been reported more than project success. Standish Group (2009) published that in the USA, only 32% of projects succeed, 44% were challenged and 24% of projects failed. Stewart (2013) further claimed that only 25% of projects remain successful. In Kenya, about 30% of organizations experience failure in their projects (Mathew, 2011). Kerzner (2013) observed that projects may fail to achieve targets and objectives due to low morale, demotivation, poorly managed project team relations and commitment. Thus, transformational top management support and behaviors is a very critical factor for better performance of various projects (Yang et al., 2011).

Belassi and Tukel (2016) argue that for every project to be successful, senior management support is required to mobilize resources for project goals. Carson (2017), the level of management support is mostly determined by management commitment. Well, performing projects start with organizational culture, a vision of what to be achieved (Lim & Mohamed 2013). Conservation projects succeed due to proper project design, realistic budget estimates, realistic time frames, effective communication; secure funding, institutional strengths. Costs, time and quality parameters need to be specified and contracted for performance assessment (De Wit, 2018). Most of the conservation projects experience many setbacks that affect the project implementation process (Muli, 2018). It is in regard to the above gaps that this study aimed to assess the determine influence of project planning on performance of elephant conservation at Tsavo National Park.

1.2 Specific Objective

The specific objective was:

- i. To determine the influence of project resource planning on performance of elephant conservation at Tsavo National Park

1.3 Research Hypotheses

Ho1 Project resource planning has no statistical significance on performance of elephant conservation at Tsavo National Park

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.2.1 Resource-Based Theory

This theory was developed by Pfeferand Salancik, (2013). This theory argues that firms possess resources that enable them to achieve competitive advantage and lead to superior long term performance. Valuable and rare resources can lead to the creation of a competitive advantage. That advantage can be sustained over longer time periods to the extent that the firm is able to protect against resource limitation, transfer or substitution (Frawley & Fahy, 2016).

In employing this theory to this study, the researcher looks at how the dependence of resources influences the project success of elephant conservation projects. The author argues that the project under study is dependent on resources, these resources ultimately originate from the environment of the donors, the environment to a considerable extent contains the organizations, the resources one organization need are thus often in the hand of other organization, resources are a basis of power, legally independent organizations can, therefore, be independent on each other (John, 2017).

2.2.2 Planning Theory

This theory guided the study in establishing the relationship between project planning and performance of conservation projects. Human is generally attributed with drawing attention to the sought distinction: what is does not necessarily lead to what should be (Wenz, 2013). Although what is may place restrictions on what can be, our human capacity to reflect on possibilities and make choices means that what is and what should be are connected by values. This connection exists whether it is recognized or not. Where applications of values are not made explicit, they are implicit in underlying cultural conditioning. The fundamental need for a position and a meaning for our lives and for our species dominates whatever system of thought we adopt. We cannot exist conceptually without such cosmologies, yet many people are unaware of the values upon which they have founded their structure of meaning (Palmer, 2014).

Recognizing this evaluative connection is crucial for planning. Due to its future orientation, planning influences what will/can be. In a just society, it must consequently raise the question of what should be by

acknowledging the role of values. What is corresponds to knowledge that is held - what ought to be corresponds to actions prior to their taking place. In consequence, planning relates to the linkage: value. It, therefore, has a normative aspect. This normative consideration must be integrated into planning on both theoretical and practical levels. In addition, recognizing planning as an "intervening variable" suggests a need to recognize the importance of multiple values. In consequence, it is necessary to consider how these values can be determined and how they can be acted upon. In a sense, then, planning is paradoxical: it is concerned with understanding the activity and process itself and is therefore descriptive. Yet simultaneously, it is concerned, in a pro-active way, with the formation of future states, and is therefore prescriptive (Watch, 2013).

2.3 Conceptual Framework

A Conceptual framework is a hypothesized model identifying the model under study and the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The dependent variable in this study is project success while the independent Variables is the influence of resource planning,

INDEPENDENT VARIABLE

Fig 2.1: Conceptual Framework

2.4 Empirical review

In his study Oluoch (2014) analyzed the determinants of effective monitoring and evaluation systems through a case study of national youth service empowerment projects (Nairobi region). The study adopted a descriptive research design and data collected using questionnaires and responses sought from managers and supervisors. The researcher utilized both descriptive and inferential analysis procedures and output. The study established that financial, human and material resources played a major role in project success.

In a study by Engwall and Jerbrant (2013), they identified a couple of mechanisms related to the resource allocation problem in a multi-project organization that is closely related to this particular case. They studied two empirical cases and in both of them, the organizations had a centralized resource planning system that allocated resources to projects based on-time schedules. The problem here was that there was almost always some project that lagged behind the schedule and hence it made the schedule created by the system impossible to use.

In Rwanda, Umulisa, Mbabazize & Shukla (2015) did a study to determine the effect of Project Resource Planning Practices on Project Performance of Agaseke Project in Kigali. The specific objectives of the research were to determine the effects of human resources planning practices on Agaseke project service quality, to analyze the effects of financial resource planning practices on the Agaseke project and to analyze the effects of Material and time resource planning practices for timely implementation of Agaseke .The study revealed that Human resource planning practices, financial resource planning practices and Material and Time resource planning practices had an influence on Agaseke project performance.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Research design is a blueprint for fulfilling objectives and answering questions. The study employed a descriptive research design to analyze the influence of project plan elements on elephant conservation projects (Kombo & Tromp, 2016). Descriptive research describes data and characteristics of a population of a phenomenon. This was an appropriate research design as it aimed at producing an accurate representation of the element under investigation, events, and situations (Torochim, 2011). It also allows the researcher to collect qualitative and quantitative data to enrichen the research. The study population comprised of technical staff from Area Administration department (Finance and Procurement section), Infrastructure development staff, Security department, and Community Wildlife services at the Tsavo East Conservation area.

Table 3. 1: Target Population

Category	Frequency
Area Management	7
Civil Works	24
Community Wildlife service	32
Security	113
Total	176

Source: Human Resource Department Tsavo Conservation area (2019)

3.2 Sampling size and Sampling technique

A sample is a subset of a population, carefully selected to represent the targeted population. According to Hyndman (2018), a sample is a subset of the population to be studied.

The choice of sample size is vital so as to avoid wastage by not being too large and to give confidence to the results of the study by not being too small (Kothari 2004). This was determined through the use of Nassiuma (2000) formula where:

$$n = \frac{N C^2}{e^2 + (N-1)e^2}$$

Where: n = Sample size,

N = Population,

C = Coefficient of variation,

e = Standard error.

C=25% is acceptable according to Nassiuma (2000), e = 0.02 and N= 202

$$n = \frac{176 \times 0.25^2}{0.02^2 + (176 - 1) 0.02^2}$$

$$n = \frac{11}{0.1325}$$

$$n = 83$$

Thus, the sample will be 83 respondents

Therefore, the sample size of this study was 83 respondents.

3.3 Data analysis and presentation.

The primary data will be collected, gathered and sorted for ease of manipulation and analysis. The data will then be edited, coded and classified where the researcher will tabulate the quantitative data for each research question and present it in frequency and percentages. These data quality checks will be done in order to eliminate errors. The analysis

will be done using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) since it helps spot data-entry errors or unusual data points and has a full set of statistical tests and the results will be presented in tables. The data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression techniques. According to Weaver (2017), descriptive statistics focus on describing the main features of a given data set in order to establish patterns and trends. The following regression model will be tested.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon$$

Where;

Y - Represents Project Performance

β_0 - represents Constant

X1 - represents risk planning

X2 - represents resource planning

X3 - represents schedule planning

β_1 to β_4 , are the coefficients of the variables to be determined by the model

ε - Represents the estimated error of the regression model

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Response Rate

Of the 83 questionnaires issued out to respondents, 76 were successfully filled and returned for analysis thus giving the study a 94 % response rate. This response rate was considered sufficient for the purpose of the study. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), a 50% response rate is adequate, 60% good and above 70% rated very well.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

The study further evaluated the views of the respondents on the influence of resource planning on performance of elephant conservation. In this section, the data collected and analyzed was on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agrees to strongly disagree

4.2.1 Resource Planning and Project Performance

The study examined the effect of resource planning on performance of elephant conservation projects. The relevant findings are as shown in Table 4.1

Table 4. 1: Resource Planning and Project Performance

Statement	N	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	Std. Dev
Project leaders shall be able to place requests on specific resources or a type of resource	76	(68)	(26)	(0)	(1)	(4)	4.54	0.901
My organization has good routines and methods to follow when performing tasks in the Projects	76	(3)	(11)	(0)	(63)	(24)	2.05	0.951
All the routines and methods for performing tasks in the conservation projects are easy to follow and understand	76	(4)	(3)	(0)	(41)	(53)	1.64	0.934
Resources are fairly utilized in development of conservation projects	76	(5)	(3)	(0)	(54)	(38)	1.83	0.971
Planning for structures to facilitate development of elephant conservation projects has been so far successful	76	(24)	(67)	(0)	(7)	(3)	4.03	0.864

It is evident from the results in Table 4.1 that most (94%) of the respondents agreed that project leaders shall be able to place requests on specific resources or a type of resource (Mean = 4.54; Std. Dev. =0.901).

Also, majority (87%) of the respondents disagreed that the organization has good routines and methods to follow when performing tasks in the Projects (Mean = 2.05; Std. Dev=0.951). On the other hand, most (94%) of the participants disagreed that all the routines and methods for performing tasks in the conservation projects are easy to follow and understand (Mean = 1.64; Std. Dev. =0.934). Lindkvist (2018) sees projects and routines as complementary modes of adaption and an organization should choose either projects or routines as a strategy to adapt to the situation.

Additionally, most (92%) of the respondents disagreed that resources are fairly utilized in the development of conservation projects (Mean = 1.83; Std. Dev. =0.971). These findings are supported by John (2017) that applying too few resources to any given activity slows progress and applying too many can cause crowding that reduces productivity and wastes resources that could be used more efficiently by other activities. Therefore, the effective and efficient allocation of scarce resources among development phases and among activities within phases is a realistic management opportunity for improving project schedule performance.

However, majority (91%) of the respondents agreed that planning for structures to facilitate the development of elephant conservation projects has been so far successful (Mean = 4.03; Std. Dev. =0.864). The findings also correspond with results and obtained from earlier research by Kebenei (2014) where most of the respondents said that that planning

for structures to facilitate development of rural health projects has been implemented successfully. Also, resources are fairly utilized in the development of health facilities in Turbo Constituency.

Most of the respondents concur that resource planning affects the performance of elephant conservation projects to a large extent. Resources such as adequate finance and competent human resource are crucial for the effectiveness of project planning and its implementation in a rapidly changing environment (Wade and Hulland, 2014).

4.3 Inferential Statistical Findings

This section documents and discusses the inferential statistical findings analyzed from the data collected in respect of the influence resource planning on conservation project performance.

4.3.1 Influence Resource Planning on Performance of Conservation Project.

The purpose was to examine the influence Resource Planning on Performance of Conservation Project. The results are shown in Table 4.2

Table 4. 2: Pearson’s Correlation between Resource Planning and Project Performance

Variable	Project Performance	
Resource Planning	Pearson Correlation	.961**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	N	76

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on the analysis of the findings, since p-value ($p=0.000$) is less than α value ($\alpha=0.01$), we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that resource planning influences conservation project performance. This is in line with a study by Ogogo, Omwenga and Paul (2018) that concluded that resource planning enhances the performance of government construction projects in Kenya.

V. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that resources are not fairly utilized in the development of conservation projects. Due to planning for structures, facilitation development of elephant conservation projects has been so far successful. The organization should put down ways in which they will fund for resources before the project commences and also have a clear resource plan on how the resources will be utilised to the end of the project. Project managers should also be keen in monitoring the project process. Lack good routines and methods and are not easy to follow and understand when performing tasks in the projects hence the conclusion resource planning affects performance of elephant conservation projects to a large extent.

VI. RECOMMEDATIONS

The study recommends project managers to develop project resource plan that should contain every aspect that pertains to every resource necessary for project from beginning to end. In addition to helping the manager determine the resources needed at hand, planning for the project is arguably the most efficient way to organize for the appropriate and effective use of such resources. These will essentially transforms the project from a vision to a time-based plan.

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